

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

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XORIJIY TAJRIBA**

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KIRISH SO‘ZI

HURMATLI ANJUMAN ISHTIROKCHILARI, MEHMONLAR, HAMKASBLAR, AZIZ TALABALAR!

Sizlarni Toshkent menejment va iqtisodiyot instituti tomonidan tashkil etilayotgan mazkur Respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumanida qutlashdan mamnunmiz.

Qadrli anjuman ishtirokchilari, bugun biz mamlakatimizda biznesni qo‘llab-quvvatlash va iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirish masalalari bo‘yicha amalga oshirilayotgan ishlar, mavjud muammolar va ularni bartaraf etish yo‘llari, hamda bu yo‘nalishdagi xorijiy tajribalarni muhokama qilish uchun to‘plandik.

Habaringiz bor, Prezidentimiz tomonidan 2024-yilni O‘zbekistonda “Yoshlar va biznesni qo‘llab-quvvatlash yili”, deb e‘lon qilinganida, inson qadrini ulug‘lash va aholimiz manfaatlarini ta‘minlash uchun kuchli iqtisodiyot barpo etish asosiy vazifalarimizdan biri ekanligi ta‘kidlangan edi.

Shunga ko‘ra, joriy yilda iqtisodiyotimizga xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb etishga, tadbirkorlik va xususiy mulk uchun keng imkoniyatlar yaratishga, ilm-fan, innovatsiya, IT kabi sohalarni, “yashil” va raqamli texnologiyalarni rivojlantirishga alohida e‘tibor qaratilmoqda.

Chunki, barqaror va kuchli iqtisodiyot nafaqat iqtisodiyot subyektlari uchun, balki jamiyatimizning kelajagi va farovonligi uchun ham juda katta ahamiyatga ega.

Hozirgi kunda, bizning jamiyatimiz - raqamli transformatsiya davriga qadam qo‘ydi. Raqamlashtirish jarayoni - biznes jarayonlaridan tortib, davlat xizmatlariga qadar ko‘plab sohalarni qamrab olmoqda.

Albatta bunday o‘zgarishlar, texnologik taraqqiyotga hamohang ravishda, qo‘shimcha imkoniyatlarni ochishga va rivojlanishning yangi strategiyalarini ishlab chiqishga keng imkoniyatlar yaratmoqda.

Lekin shu bilan bir qatorda, iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirish va bunday sharoitda biznesni rivojlantirish jarayonlarida, o‘ziga xos muammolar va turli savollar ham yuzaga kelmoqda.

Bunday masalalarni o‘rganib, uning yechimlarini topish uchun Toshkent menejment va iqtisodiyot institutining professor-o‘qituvchilari tomonidan ham turli ilmiy tadqiqotlarni olib borish yo‘lga qo‘yilgan. Ularning tadqiqotlari natijalaridan - o‘quv jarayonlarida, ta‘lim sifatini oshirish maqsadlarida, keng foydalaniladi.

Bu o‘z navbatida, institutda menejment, iqtisodiyot va axborot texnologiyalari sohasida tayyorlanadigan malakali mutaxassislarining nafaqat nazariy bilimlarini, balki amaliy ko‘nikmalarini ham oshirishga hizmat qiladi.

Bundan tashqari, institutda innovatsion dasturlar va loyihalar orqali talabalarni yangi texnologiyalar bilan tanishtirish, ularda raqamli iqtisodiyot va global biznes muhitida raqobatbardosh bo‘lish uchun zarur bo‘lgan ko‘nikmalarni shakllantirishga yordam beradi.

Bugungi anjumanda, biz raqamlashtirish va biznesni rivojlantirish jarayonlarida uchraydigan muammolarni chuqur o‘rganishni va ilmiy asoslangan yechimlarni izlashni o‘z oldimizga maqsad qilib qo‘yganmiz.

Shu bilan birga, asosiy anjuman va sho‘ba yig‘ilishlarida mazkur masalalar bo‘yicha xorijiy tajribalarni ham tahlil qilish orqali, biz qanday yechimlar topishimiz mumkinligini muhokama qilamiz.

Bugun sizlarning e‘tiboringizga taqdim etiladigan taqdimotlar va fikrlar - bizni zamonaviy iqtisodiyotning yangi talablariga mos keladigan biznes modellarni yaratishga ilhomlantiradi.

Maqsadimiz – bu kabi ilmiy-amaliy uchrashuvlar orqali ilm ahlini va biznes vakillarini bir joyda jamlab, biznesni qo‘llab-quvvatlash mexanizmlarini hamda iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirish jarayonlarini yanada takomillashtirish bo‘yicha asoslangan takliflar va amaliy tavsiyalarni ishlab chiqishga imkoniyatlar yaratishdan iboratdir.

Biz bu jarayonda, o‘z tajribamizni almashish va birgalikda muammolarni hal qilish uchun yangi g‘oyalarni kashf etishni maqsad qilamiz.

Umid qilamanki, anjumanimiz samarali va foydali bo‘ladi.

Har biringizning ishtirokingiz va hissangiz bu jarayonda juda muhim.

Keling, birgalikda yangiliklarga ochiq bo‘lib, innovatsion yechimlarni izlaylik!

Bugungi anjuman ishiga va unda ishtirok etayotgan barcha ishtirokchilarning ilmiy-ijodiy faoliyatlariga ulkan muvaffaqiyatlar tilaymiz!

**Axmedov Xojiakbarxon Dilshatovich,
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5-SHO'BA.

BIZNES VA BOSHQARUVDA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT HAMDA SUN'IY INTELLEKT TEXNOLOGIYALARI

A CREATIVE IDEA - THE KEY TO DEVELOPING AN INNOVATIVE ECOSYSTEM

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Abstract: The article examines how the perception and attitude towards innovation and innovative technologies is being transformed in modern conditions. Today, a creative idea is the key to the development of an innovation ecosystem, as well as a tool in creating effective, competitive clusters and business models, new jobs and additional opportunities for entrepreneurship development. A creative idea plus entrepreneurship unites and develops various industries and areas.

Key words: creative idea, creativity, human capital, innovation ecosystem, disruptive innovation, sustainable innovation, effective innovation, effects, business model.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada zamonaviy sharoitda innovatsiyalar va innovatsion texnologiyalarga nisbatan qarash va munosabat qanday o'zgarib borayotgani ko'rib chiqiladi. Bugungi kunda ijodiy g'oya innovatsion ekotizimni rivojlantirishning kaliti, shuningdek, samarali, raqobatbardosh klasterlar va biznes modellarini yaratish, yangi ish o'rinlari va tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirish uchun qo'shimcha imkoniyatlar yaratish vositasidir. Ijodiy g'oya va tadbirkorlik turli soha va sohalarni birlashtiradi va rivojlantiradi.

Kalit so'zlar: ijodiy g'oya, ijodkorlik, inson kapitali, innovatsion ekotizim, buzuvchi innovatsiya, barqaror innovatsiya, samarali innovatsiya, effektlar, biznes modeli.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается как в современных условиях трансформируется восприятие и отношение к инновациям и инновационным технологиям. Сегодня креативная идея – залог развития инновационной экосистемы, а также инструмент в создании эффективных, конкурентоспособных кластеров и бизнес-моделей, новых рабочих мест и дополнительных возможностей развития предпринимательства. Креативная идея плюс предприимчивость объединяет и развивает различные отрасли и сферы.

Ключевые слова: креативная идея, творчество, человеческий капитал, инновационная экосистема, подрывные инновации, устойчивые инновации, эффективные инновации, эффекты, бизнес-модель.

In modern conditions of transition to an innovative type of development, the need for highly intelligent innovative technologies is growing. As you know, innovation is, first of all, an idea embodied in a product or process. Any business starts with a business idea. Over the past 10 years, the term "creative economy" has become increasingly used - the economy of the "next generation", where the main capitalized value is new ideas. It is an economy based on innovation, novelty and creative products. [1]

Today, effective innovation is the result of creative ideas. Creativity (from the Latin creatio - creativity) is a person's ability to deviate from standard opinions, rules and patterns. In addition, creativity presupposes the presence of a progressive approach, imagination and originality. [2]

Creativity is possessed by intellectually developed people with a high degree of creative ability. The difference between creative abilities and creativity is that creative abilities are defined as personality qualities, and creativity as the manifestation of these qualities in mental activity. Creativity presupposes the ability for an individual to perceive, transform and create new information.

Human capital plays a critical role in the generation, development and implementation of creative ideas. Innovative solutions are provided by people with deep domain knowledge or diverse experience, research and development skills to more effectively develop and translate creative ideas into reality.

A creative idea contributes to the creation of "disruptive", "sustainable" and "effective" innovations, thereby developing the country's innovation ecosystem. [3]

The currency of the creative economy is the idea. Its development requires knowledge and talent. Startups can be called creative businesses, and intellectual property is the DNA of the creative economy. In Europe, the creative and cultural sectors create 2.5 times more jobs than the automotive industry. [4]

A creative idea embodied in innovation is an innovative activity that has several effects:

- despite the product's life cycle, by improving it, assigning additional functions and properties, it increases consumer need and demand, thereby returning it to the stage of growth and development.

- creates additional opportunities for the development of small and medium-sized businesses, women's entrepreneurship, for people with disabilities and thereby new jobs;
- contribute to the revival of national traditions and customs, the development of healthy, socially responsible youth;
- develops business models and clusters around itself.

It should be noted that the effects of innovative activity solve the problems of innovative development of the country specified in the "Strategy for Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022 - 2026".

The task of further development of human capital through the development of creative abilities, innovative entrepreneurship and innovation is one of the most important areas. Today, our tasks include employing university graduates, creating jobs, and organizing production facilities that require high intellectual knowledge. After all, current students should become the driving force behind the formation of a creative economy in Uzbekistan.

In countries around the world, the creative economy has today become a priority. According to available data, the global creative economy market will reach a trillion dollars by 2024. This contributes significantly to the growth of the gross domestic product of developing countries. The global economy is experiencing high growth rates.

The global economy is experiencing high growth rates. In the future, due to the rapid pace of development of the creative economy, inequality between the economies of civilized and developing countries will steadily increase. That is why science and education play an important role in the development of each sphere. [4]

A clear example of such a creative idea is the Harry Potter series of novels written by JK Rowling¹. It is characteristic that the novel was written in 1990-1995, and published in 1997 - this is a period when interest in books and reading lost popularity, especially among young people, and the need for book products decreased. The novel distinguished itself for its creativity and already in 2000 became the most popular among young people.

It has become a unique example and the basis for an incredibly successful business model that has contributed to the creation of large numbers of jobs and the development of entrepreneurship. The increase in demand for reading has increased the need and development of:

activities of printing houses. The Harry Potter books have increased interest in reading among young people and by 2019, more than 3 million copies had been sold, making the series the best-selling series in literary history. This massive recognition generated significant revenue and brought international attention to the project.

educational and entertainment programs. The novel inspired the creation of educational programs and courses, for example, for learning English based on Rowling's books. Recreational and enrichment activities are also being developed to further explore the literary and cultural aspects of the work.

professional translation services of fiction. The novels have been translated into almost all languages of the world, which has contributed to even greater distribution and recognition on a global level.

development of the film industry. Based on the success of the books, a film series was created that became the third highest-grossing film in history. The success of the films resulted in significant financial income.

development of tourism and museum industry. Film locations, including sound stages and props, have been converted into museums and tourist attractions. This has attracted a large number of locals and tourists, boosting the tourism industry.

development of small business and merchandising. The popularity of Harry Potter gave impetus to the creation and development of small businesses engaged in sewing costumes and making souvenirs. Harry Potter has become one of the most successful brands in the field of merchandising. A huge number of products, from toys and clothing to stationery and home decor, have been created based on the Potter universe.

creation of amusement parks. The creation of theme parks such as The Wizarding World of Harry Potter at Universal Studios allowed fans to immerse themselves in a world of magic and adventure. These parks became a significant source of income and attracted millions of visitors.

digital and interactive products. With the development of digital technologies, new forms of interaction with the world of Harry Potter have emerged. VR games, mobile apps (such as Harry Potter: Wizards Unite), and interactive sites such as Pottermore (now Wizarding World) allowed fans to immerse themselves in the world of magic digitally.

franchising and partnerships. The Harry Potter brand actively uses franchising and partnerships to expand its influence. Examples include collaborations with major brands to create limited edition products and joint marketing campaigns that help maintain interest in the Potter universe.

¹ Британская писательница, автор серии романов о Гарри Поттере.

As a copyright owner, JK Rowling went from living on welfare to becoming a multimillionaire in five years. According to the American magazine Forbes, in December 2019, JK Rowling was in first place on the list of the highest paid writers. Her total income was \$92 million. [5]

This example shows how a creative idea can increase product demand and promote service entrepreneurship, influencing different areas of business and culture, creating a diverse and sustainable business model.

Therefore, nurturing a cultural and creative personality is important in creating human capital and national creative ideas, which contributes to the development of the country's innovation ecosystem. Ultimately, creative ideas implemented in the form of innovations not only contribute to the development of innovative technologies and processes, but also ensure the dynamic development of existing products and services.

This creates a healthy and competitive innovation ecosystem that promotes economic growth and social progress.

A highly intelligent entrepreneur, due to his entrepreneurial spirit, is able to turn a creative idea into an effective business model or cluster.

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Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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